

REAL-TIME VIDEO PROCESSING WITH FPGAS

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Abstract

In this article, I would like to talk about real-time video streaming implementation on FPGA and how to correctly build the structure of the whole project. How to choose the right color space. How to convert from one color space to another? How to use shift registers to speed up an algorithm on an FPGA? How to build a memory buffer for real time video processing and why to use an FIFO buffer instead of writing the data directly into the SDRAM and why it is good using the different filters and which filters are better to use and when.

Keywords: FPGA, real time, FIFO, OV7670, RGB, YCbCr.

Introduction

Machine vision is first of all image capture from video camera. Before the start of the process of video detection or classification of objects in the neural network, the video signal has to travel a long way, from an analog signal of a certain frequency at the input of the video matrix to a fully-fledged video, where certain transformations will take place and the computer can accurately identify and classify objects. There are several types of video sensors. In our project we will use a cheap video module OV7670[1]. This module transmits video data over an eight bit bus via a GPIO[2] interface. We can configure it using the protocol Serial Camera Control Bus (SCCB)[3], this protocol is compatible with the protocol I2C, although there are other video modules where you can configure the video module using the SPI protocol. The initial resolution will be VGA 640x480 pixels. The color space we can choose from YUV/YCbCr 4:2:2, RGB565/555, GRB 4:2:2. The choice of format and color space depends on

the project. You can find a ready-to-use Verilog language module of the OV7670 from the manufacturer here[4]. Sometimes several color spaces are used simultaneously in the same project. The FIFO buffer[5] is very important because the video is processed in real time and we can't wait for the whole frame and then process it. We need to build two the FIFO buffers for two lines of the width of our frame and three pixels of the third line we will take directly from the stream and in this way we can already do some transformations such as filtering or changing the color space. The important thing to note is that after capturing video from the camera we don't write these data directly to SDRAM, but convert them and only after that we can write the data to SDRAM.

Project architecture

Picture 1.1 shows the architecture of video capture and basic processing in real time, followed by the display of the image.

Pic 1.1 Project architecture

Video capture module

Video capture will be in VGA 640 X 480 resolution, in YCbCr 4:2:2 color format, but we can also receive video in RGB 565 format, at 30fps. The module receives from the camera the vertical sync control signals (V_SYNC_IN) to send the frame and the horizontal sync signal (H_SYNC_IN) for each line of the frame

Pic 1.2 RGB 565 format by two data bytes

Also, the module operates at a frequency of 50MHz which is generated by the PLL of our FPGA. The module generates and transmits the control signals to the color space conversion module.

Color Space Modules

Grayscale conversions

We receive our video in RGB565 format. It is not always convenient for us to work in this color space for various reasons. First, to reduce the size, we can convert RGB565, which takes 2 bytes of information in a one-byte grayscale. Where all grayscale is stored in one byte [0]...[255]. We can do the conversion in two ways. The first way is a mathematical conversion and is done by formula 1.1.

$$Y = 0.299R + 0.587G + 0.114B \quad (1.1)$$

Where we multiply each pixel of each channel by a certain value and add it up, the output is one 8-bit grayscale channel. But from an FPGA perspective this is not the best use of resources. It is much more efficient to shift registers Formula 1.2 demonstrates this.

$$Y = (R \gg 2) + (R \gg 5) + (G \gg 1) + (G \gg 4) + (B \gg 4) + (B \gg 5) \quad (1.2)$$

When using a shift register, the conversion is very fast and this algorithm is suitable for real-time video processing.

RGB565 to YCbCr 4:2:2 color space conversion module

Sometimes we need to switch from one color space to another. YCbCr 4:2:2 color space is not always a convenient format, it is much more convenient to work with YCbCr 4:4:4 color space. In the YCbCr 4:2:2 color space, we cannot transmit data in one clock cycle, but the format of YCbCr 4:4:4 we can transmit data in one clock cycle, in this sequence Y Cb Cr. Such a conversion reduces signal processing time. There are two kinds of conversion from RGB565 to YCbCr 4:2:2 color space. The mathematical conversion looks like this:

$$Y = 16 + (0.2567890625 * R) + (0.50412890625 * G) + (0.09790625 * B) \quad (2.1)$$

$$Cb = 128 + (0.14822265625 * R) + (0.2909921875 * G) + (0.43921484375 * B) \quad (2.2)$$

and the whole frame. The camera operates at 25MHz and to provide this frequency we will use the PLL of our FPGA development board and create a CLC_25MHz signal. Since the camcorder transmits data on an eight bit bus, it has to divide each pixel in RGB 565 format by two data bytes.

$$Cr = 128 + (0.4392148437 * R) + (0.3677890625 * G) + (0.071442578125 * B) \quad (2.3)$$

At the output we get 8-bit YCbCr. But this is not the best way to convert in FPGA environment, it is much more effective to use a shift register. The formula for the shift register:

$$Y = 16 + (((R \ll 6) + (R \ll 1) + (G \ll 7) + G + (B \ll 4) + (B \ll 3) + B) \gg 8) \quad (3.1)$$

$$Cb = 128 + (((-((R \ll 5) + (R \ll 2) + (R \ll 1))) - ((G \ll 6) + (G \ll 3) + (G \ll 1) + (B \ll 7) - (B \ll 4))) \gg 8) \quad (3.2)$$

$$Cr = 128 + (((R \ll 7) - (R \ll 4) - ((G \ll 6) + (G \ll 5) - (G \ll 1) - ((B \ll 4) + (B \ll 3)))) \gg 8) \quad (3.3)$$

Noise filtering

Noise is of two types, constant noise from the camera itself in the form of colored dots and from random exterior noise resulting created by various external factors such as atmospheric electromagnetic interference. In any case, we must filter out that noise in order to improve overall video quality.

Median filter

The median filter works well at removing impulse noise from an image whilst retaining and preserving image edges. The median filter finds the average value, but does not average it out, but chooses from the presented set of values.

Pic 1.3 The median filter

The filter works fast, because it does not need to perform any calculations, it just compares the numbers. To implement it on FPGA we have to build a 3X3 matrix that slides over the image taking 9 values and sorting those values into ascending order and outputs one average value of all 9. The FPGA implementation consists of the comparators and multiplexers.

Pic 1.4 3X3 matrix that slides over the image

Gaussian filter

The Gaussian filter is highly effective at cleaning images from noise, its only disadvantage is that images can be a smooth. In this filter we multiply the 3X3 matrix, or as it is called the filter kernel, by the image, but with one difference. The Gaussian filter kernel is already ready and we just need to add it to our code.

	1	2	1
1/16	2	4	2
	1	2	1

Pic 1.5 Kernel gaussian filter

FIFO buffers

In real time applications we will not save the video directly in SDRAM as it takes quite a long time. We will use 2 FIFO buffers. In FIFO_1, we will store the data after applying a grayscale filter or color space conversion and in FIFO_2, we will store the data after the median filter and from there we will directly output to the VGA display. We can start to use the filter when we read only two lines of pixels from the frame and take the first 3 pixels directly from the stream. This allows us to form a 3X3 matrix window and not have to wait for the whole frame to come in. In our case we have to build two FIFO buffers of 320 pixels each (frame width). The write clock is 50MHz and the read clock is 100MHz. A FIFO buffer is a dual port RAM that allows you to write and read on different clocks at the same time. It is easy to implement using Quartus[6] or Vivado[7] embedded IP directory tooling, depending on which development FPGA board is used.

Pic 1.6. 2 line FIFO buffers

VGA display

Most FPGA development boards have a VGA or HDMA display output. The embedded IP Quartus or Vivado catalog also has ready-made solutions for these displays.

Conclusion

A real time system for capturing and preprocessing video was described. This architecture works without storing it on a memory card or SDRAM[8]. Everything happens in real time, without any delays. Video can be saved before displaying it, so it would not affect the performance of the whole system. Conversion to a grayscale filter is not necessary, just after the conversion is significantly safe time processing the video signal and space for its storage.

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